

Determination of Cadmium and Lead in Sewage Sludge from the Middle Region (Misrata, Msallata and Tarhūnah Cities) of Libya

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Abstract : The concentrations of cadmium and lead in sewage sludge samples were determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrometric Method. Samples of sewage sludge were obtained from three sewage treatment plants localised in Middle Region of Libya (Misrata, Msallata and Tarhūnah cities). The results shows that, the mean levels of Cadmium for all regions are ranges from 81 to 123.4 ppm and these values are higher than the limitations for the international standard which are not registered more than 50 ppm (dry weight) in USA, Egypt and the EU countries. While, the lead concentrations are ranged from 8.0 to 189.2 ppm and all values are within the standard limits which graduated between (275-613) ppm.

Keywords : cadmium, lead, sewage, spectrometry

Conference Title : ICCB 2014 : International Conference on Chemistry and Biochemistry

Conference Location : Los Angeles, USA

Conference Dates : September 29-30, 2014